

A NON - HEURISTIC APPROACH TO STRESS PARTITIONING PARAMETERS IN MICROMECHANICS

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ABSTRACT

The elastic constants of unidirectional fiber composite material are commonly determined by rule of mixtures. Micromechanics theory based on constant strain principle lead to good accuracy in the prediction of longitudinal Young's modulus, and major Poisson's ratio. However, the analytical models based on constant stress principle lead to poor prediction of transverse Young's modulus and shear modulus. The modified rule of mixtures based on stress partitioning parameters provide better results. In general, a heuristic assumption of 0.5 is used for the parameters. An emphasis is given in this paper to study the parameters with respect to the self consistent model. A general procedure has been recommended to compute the stress partitioning parameters. It has been observed that the improvement in the accuracy of stress partitioning parameters minimize the error in the prediction of transverse Young's modulus and shear modulus. This approach facilitates the application of rule of mixtures uniformly to all the elastic constants. The results show that this is a viable approach.

KEY WORDS: Micromechanics; Elastic moduli; Rule of mixtures; Unidirectional; Stress partitioning parameters.

1. INTRODUCTION

The stress analysis and design of fiber-matrix composite materials are governed by the compliance and stiffness coefficients. The stiffness or compliance matrix can be expressed as functions of the elastic moduli and Poisson's ratios of unidirectional lamina. The four elastic constants of an unidirectional composite material are; longitudinal Young's modulus, transverse Young's modulus, major Poisson's ratio, and shear modulus. These constants are commonly determined from Micromechanics, based on rule of mixtures theory. For an axially loaded lamina, the stretch of the fiber and matrix are assumed same, which lead to constant strain principle. The analytical model based on this assumption lead to satisfactory prediction of longitudinal Young's modulus and major Poisson's ratio. Transverse Young's modulus

and shear modulus are based on constant stress principle, where the area of cross section is assumed same for both fiber and matrix. This assumption is true by considering the cross section of the lamina as rectangular. However, fiber is a thin cylinder with circular cross section and it is surrounded by a hollow cylinder of matrix; which violates the constant area assumption. Also, the constant stress principle based on constant area assumption implicitly assume that the loads on fiber and matrix are same. For most of the composite laminae, fiber being stronger than the matrix, the load shared by the fiber would be greater and hence the stress. These differences in constant stress principle lead to the poor prediction of transverse Young's modulus and shear modulus, compared to the experimental values.

Modified rule of mixtures theory [1] eliminate these differences by partitioning the fiber and matrix stresses through a suitable parameter, the stress partitioning parameter. The success of this approach is based on predicting a correct value for the stress partitioning parameters. A typical value of 0.5 is commonly used for the parameters by heuristic approach [1-5], which gives better result only for some fiber - matrix combinations, and volume fractions.

An alternate approach is to use a self consistent model based on theory of elasticity. This approach provide excellent results and successfully used in most of the commercial software. In this paper the modified rule of mixtures theory is combined with elasticity theory in order to derive a unified relation for the stress partitioning parameters. The stress partitioning parameters determined by this approach minimize the error in transverse and shear moduli for given fiber volume fraction.

2. THEORY

2.1 Modified Rule of Mixtures Matrix being a weaker constituent in most of the composites, the stress on the matrix can be normalized with respect to the fiber stress.

$$\eta_y = \frac{\sigma_{ny}}{\sigma_{fy}}, \quad 0 < \eta_y \leq 1; \quad \eta_s = \frac{\sigma_{ns}}{\sigma_{fs}}, \quad 0 < \eta_s \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

The ratio of matrix transverse stress(σ_{ny}) to fiber transverse stress(σ_{fy}) is defined as the transverse stress partitioning parameter(η_y). The shear stress partitioning parameter η_s , is defined as the ratio of matrix shear stress(σ_{ns}) to fiber shear stress(σ_{fs}). The transverse and shear elastic moduli equations can be written as [1];

$$\frac{1}{E_y} = \frac{1}{(V_f + \eta_y V_m)} \left[\frac{V_f}{E_f} + \eta_y \frac{V_m}{E_m} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1}{G} = \frac{1}{(V_f + \eta_s V_m)} \left[\frac{V_f}{G_f} + \eta_s \frac{V_m}{G_m} \right] \quad (3)$$

The successful application of this model depends on the accuracy of the stress partitioning parameters, which demands for a unified theory to determine them.

2.2 Elasticity Theory The shear and transverse moduli of composite material can be derived from the theory of elasticity [6-8]. The axial and transverse shear modulus can be expressed as a function of the elastic constants of fiber and matrix [6].

$$\text{Axial shear modulus, } G = G_m + \frac{V_f}{\left\{ \frac{1}{(G_f - G_m)} + \frac{V_m}{2G_m} \right\}} \quad (4)$$

Transverse shear modulus,

$$G_y = G_m + \frac{V_f}{\left\{ \frac{1}{(G_f - G_m)} + \frac{V_m}{2G_m} + \frac{V_m}{2(k_m + G_m)} \right\}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Transverse Young's modulus, } E_y = \frac{4k_y G_y}{k_y + M G_y} \quad (6)$$

where,

$$M = 1 + \frac{4k_y v_x^2}{E_x}; \quad k_y = k_m + \frac{V_f}{\left\{ \frac{1}{(k_f - k_m)} + \frac{V_m}{(k_m + G_m)} \right\}}$$

$$k_f = \frac{G_f}{1 - 2\nu_f}; \quad k_m = \frac{G_m}{1 - 2\nu_m}; \quad G_m = \frac{E_m}{2(1 + \nu_m)}; \quad G_f = \frac{E_f}{2(1 + \nu_f)}$$

The prediction of the transverse Young's modulus and shear modulus of unidirectional composite materials are based on the above equations [9].

2.3 Stress Partitioning Parameters The shear stress partitioning parameter from equation (3), can be written as;

$$\eta_s = \frac{G_m V_f (G - G_f)}{G_f V_m (G_m - G)} \quad (7)$$

Expressing the axial shear modulus as given in equation (4), the above equation can be simplified as;

$$\eta_s = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{G_m}{G_f} \right) \quad (8)$$

The shear stress partitioning parameter is independent of the fiber volume fraction as indicated by Tsai and Hahn [1]. From equation (2), the transverse normal stress partitioning parameter can be expressed as;

$$\eta_y = \frac{E_m V_f (E_f - E_y)}{E_f V_m (E_y - E_m)} \quad (9)$$

Expressing E_y as given in equation (6), and simplifying, the above equation reduces to;

$$\eta_y = \frac{E_m V_f}{E_f V_m} \left[\frac{N_1 - N_2 V_f - N_3 V_f^2}{D_1 + D_2 V_f + D_3 V_f^2} \right] \quad (10)$$

where,

$$N_1 = (k_f + G_m)(E_f L_2 - 4k_m G_m)(L_1)$$

$$N_2 = 4G_m^2(k_f - k_m)(L_1) + (E_f L_2 + 4k_m G_m)(L_3)$$

$$N_3 = G_m(k_f - k_m)(G_f - G_m)(2E_f L_2 + 4k_m G_m)$$

$$D_1 = (k_f + G_m)(4k_m G_m - E_m L_2)(L_1)$$

$$D_2 = 4G_m^2(k_f - k_m)(L_1) + (E_m L_2 + 4k_m G_m)(L_3)$$

$$D_3 = G_m(k_f - k_m)(G_f - G_m)(2E_m L_2 + 4k_m G_m)$$

$$L_1 = G_f(k_m + 2G_m) + k_m G_m$$

$$L_2 = (k_m + G_m)$$

$$L_3 = k_m(k_f + G_m)(G_f - G_m)$$

The simplification lead to a term of $\frac{V_f^2}{E_x}$ in the denominator of equation (10). The contribution of this term is negligibly small, and hence it has been neglected. The equation (10) determines an accurate value of transverse stress partitioning parameter for a given fiber volume fraction. Modified rule of mixtures theory, then becomes efficient in the prediction of transverse Young's modulus with minimum error. This combined theory uses rule of mixtures to determine the modulus, while the stress partitioning parameter is based on elasticity equations. Such a combination may be called as quasi-elasticity theory.

3. APPLICATION

Various fiber and matrix combinations were used to study the behavior of transverse stress partitioning parameter with respect to fiber volume fraction. A typical variation of the parameter for Graphite (T 300)/Epoxy, and E-Glass/Epoxy lamina is given in Figures 1-2. The transverse Young's modulus determined by this approach is compared with the values obtained from a typical commercial software [9]. This software is based on theory of elasticity and hence provide a better comparison for the present method, and the comparison is given in Table 1.

The transverse stress partitioning parameter for other combinations of fibers and matrix are given in Table 2. Three different volume fractions are chosen; one for lower range ($V_f = 0.2$), one for mid range ($V_f = 0.5$), and one for higher range ($V_f = 0.8$).

TABLE 1 COMPARISON OF TRANSVERSE YOUNG'S MODULUS

Lamina	V_f	η_y	E_y (GPA) (Present method)	% Error	E_y (GPA) ($\eta_y = 0.5$)	% Error	E_y (GPA) (COMPCAL)
Graphite	0.2	0.431	5.4	1.1	5.14	3.7	5.34
(T-300)/	0.5	0.528	9.68	0.4	10.05	4.3	9.64
Epoxy	0.8	0.559	25.39	0.9	27.7	10.1	25.17
E - Glass/	0.2	0.429	5.31	3.0	5.1	0.8	5.14
Epoxy	0.5	0.53	9.1	1.4	9.45	5.4	8.97
	0.8	0.557	21.1	1.9	22.53	9.3	20.61

TABLE 2. TRANSVERSE STRESS PARTITIONING PARAMETERS

Volume Fraction	<u>Transverse stress partitioning parameter</u> (η_y)			
	Boron/Epoxy	Kevlar/Epoxy	Gr/Aluminum	Bo/Aluminum
0.2	0.431	0.429	0.465	0.484
0.5	0.528	0.526	0.579	0.584
0.8	0.559	0.55	0.569	0.593

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The comparison of transverse Young's modulus for different plies in Table 1, shows that the present method is efficient in predicting the values with minimum error. The percentage of error for the present non-heuristic method is relatively minimum compared to the heuristic method.. In heuristic method, it can be observed that the error is minimum for lower volume fractions, and it increases for the mid-range or higher volume fractions. In the present method, the error decreases from lower range of volume fractions to mid-range of volume fractions, and increases from mid-range to higher range of volume fractions. For most of the practical applications, volume fraction is in the mid-range and hence the present method is very efficient in the prediction of elastic moduli.

It can be observed that the transverse stress partitioning parameter (equation 10) is a function of the elastic moduli of fiber and matrix. Also, it is a function of fiber volume fraction and it can be observed from Figure 1 and Figure 2 that the variation is nonlinear. To demonstrate the sensitivity of the transverse stress partitioning parameter, transverse Young's modulus is plotted as a function of the above parameter in Figure 3. The variation in percentage of error in the modulus is given in Figure 4, as a function of the partitioning parameter. These figures show that there is a need to predict the partitioning parameter accurately in order to minimize the error. The present method provides a unified relation to determine the stress partitioning parameter.

The shear stress partitioning parameter is a function of fiber shear modulus and matrix shear modulus, and it is independent of fiber volume fraction [1]. A typical value of this parameter for different composite plies are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3. SHEAR STRESS PARTITIONING PARAMETER

Graphite (T-300)/Epoxy	0.507
E-Glass/Epoxy	0.521
Boron/Epoxy	0.504
Kevlar/Epoxy	0.513
Graphite/Aluminum	0.647
E-Glass/Aluminum	0.965
Graphite/Titanium	0.723
E-Glass/Titanium	1.207

The error in shear modulus induced by assuming the shear stress partitioning parameter as 0.5 is relatively minimum for composites with organic matrix, compared to metal matrix composites. However, using the correct value for the partitioning parameter leads to a better prediction of shear modulus and its comparison with the results from COMPCAL [9], shows that the marriage between them is perfect.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In micromechanics of composite materials, the transverse and shear moduli determined by modified rule of mixtures theory are sensitive to the transverse and shear stress partitioning parameters. The accuracy in the stress partitioning parameters lead to better prediction of elastic moduli and minimizes the percentage of error.

The transverse stress partitioning parameter determined by the present method is a function of fiber volume fraction, in addition to the elastic moduli of fiber and matrix. This unified relation provide a better value for the parameter, and minimizes the percentage of error in transverse Young's modulus. For composites with metal matrix, the shear stress partitioning parameter need to be determined accurately for better prediction of shear modulus.

This approach facilitates the application of the rule of mixtures to all the elastic constants without any loss in accuracy. The values determined by this method are in excellent agreement with the advanced models based on theory of elasticity. The present method is a valuable addition to the modified rule of mixtures theory for class room education in the university, and a viable approach for preliminary calculations in the industry.

6. REFERENCES

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FIGURE 1 Variation of transverse stress partitioning parameter(ETA-Y Parameter) with Fiber volume fraction -- GRAPHITE (T-300) / EPOXY

FIGURE 2 Variation of transverse stress partitioning parameter(ETA-Y Parameter) with Fiber volume fraction -- E - GLASS / EPOXY

FIGURE 3 Variation of transverse Young's modulus with the stress partitioning parameter GRAPHITE (T-300) / EPOXY

FIGURE 4 Percentage of error in transverse Young's modulus with respect to the stress partitioning parameter --- GRAPHITE (T-300) / EPOXY

7. BIOGRAPHY

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